

REAL-TIME LINEAR TIME-FREQUENCY TRANSFORM

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ABSTRACT

A real-time linear time-frequency transform is proposed based on SLTF transform [2]. The proposed transform has a small time delay and a much lower computational cost than other transforms. A fast algorithm to compute the biorthogonal function and the transform coefficients is presented. Finally, the characteristics of the proposed transform is compared with the original SLTF.

1 INTRODUCTION

Time-frequency (TF) transforms are of interest to many areas due to their natural decomposition of a signal into a function localized in both time and frequency. Specifically, Gabor transform has the optimal localization in the TF domain [1]. SLTF transform maintains the same optimality of Gabor transform. Moreover, it overcomes two main problems of the critically-sampled TF transforms: stability and localization of the window and its biorthogonal function [2].

In many applications, like telephony speech coding, a real-time processing is needed where time delay is very crucial. Gabor and SLTF transforms, however, are not suitable for real-time processing since the window and its biorthogonal function are of infinite length, i.e., the entire signal has to be received before processing. Real-time processing requires truncating the infinite length window and its biorthogonal function. This truncation, however, includes reconstruction error and degradation of some transform characteristics like numerical stability and localization of the window or its biorthogonal function in the frequency domain [3].

In this paper, a real-time critically-sampled TF transform will be developed based on SLTF [2]. this transform has a small time delay and a much lower computational cost than SLTF with no changes in the characteristics of SLTF (some characteristics, like the numerical stability, have been improved). The proposed transform leads to an exact reconstruction of the signal, and not just an approximation, as the case in [3].

The proposed transform is developed as follows: In Section 3, the aperiodic discrete SLTF is developed. Aperiodicity is needed for real-time transform since in

periodic case, the first coefficients strongly depend on the last part of the signal, i.e., one has to wait to get the entire signal to compute these coefficients. In Section 4, it will be proven that for the aperiodic discrete SLTF, the biorthogonal function for any window of length $\leq 2N$ will be of the same length. This means that using any window of length $\leq 2N$ and its *naturally* short biorthogonal function will lead to a small delay ($\leq \frac{3N}{2}$) TF transform with an exact reconstruction of the signal. In Section 5, an efficient method to compute the transform coefficients is presented. In Section 6, a comparison study of the characteristics of the proposed transform with the original SLTF is conducted.

2 SLTF TRANSFORM

In [2], a new critically-sampled linear TF Transform was proposed. This Transform is defined for a continuous signal $x(t)$ as

$$x(t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_{m,n} h_m(t) \text{csin} \frac{\pi(n + \frac{1}{2})t}{T} \quad (1)$$

where $a_{m,n}$ are the transform coefficients, $\text{csin}(\cdot)$ stands for $\cos(\cdot)$ for even m and $\sin(\cdot)$ for odd m , and $h_m(t)$ is the Gaussian window, with rms-width σ , shifted to the center of the m^{th} window, i.e.,

$$h_m(t) \triangleq \sqrt{\sigma}^{-1} \exp\left(\frac{-\pi}{2\sigma^2} (t - (m + 0.5)T)^2\right)$$

Compared with other TF transforms, SLTF has several advantages that makes it suitable for many applications. First, SLTF is a linear critically-sampled transform. This simplifies performing the synthesis transform (from the TF domain to the original domain) after filtering. This is in contrast to bilinear transforms where difficulties are encountered in getting back the signal from the TF domain or the over-sampled transforms where iterative methods are needed for the synthesis transform [4]. Compared to other linear critically-sampled TF transforms, this transform has two major advantages: stability and localization of both the window and its biorthogonal function [2].

In the next section an aperiodic discretization of this transform is developed.

3 APERIODIC SLTF TRANSFORM

In [2], discrete SLTF transform was derived after forcing both the signal and the window to be periodic. This involves a substantial change from the natural structure of the transform. In addition, in the periodic case, the first coefficients depend strongly on the last part of the signal as well as the first part. Here, an aperiodic discretization of SLTF is developed, i.e. neither the window nor the signal are assumed to be periodic.

The signal $x(t)$ is assumed to have finite duration MT which has been regularly sampled at an interval T with further regular sub-samples at an interval $\frac{T}{N}$. The discretization of (1) for any window $h(t)$ gives the following aperiodic finite discrete synthesis transform

$$x\left(\frac{k+\frac{1}{2}}{N/T}\right) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} a_{m,n} h_m\left(\frac{k+\frac{1}{2}}{N/T}\right) \text{csin} \frac{\pi(n+\frac{1}{2})(k+\frac{1}{2})}{N}$$

Denoting $x\left(\frac{k+\frac{1}{2}}{N/T}\right)$ by $x(k)$ and $h_m\left(\frac{k+\frac{1}{2}}{N/T}\right)$ by $h_m(k)$ gives

$$x(k) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} a_{m,n} h_m(k) \text{csin} \frac{\pi(n+\frac{1}{2})(k+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \quad (2)$$

To put (2) in matrix form, define $\mathbf{x}_m$, $\mathbf{a}_m$, and H_m as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_m &\triangleq [x(mN) : x(mN + N - 1)]^T, \\ \mathbf{a}_m &\triangleq [a_{m,0} : a_{m,N-1}]^T, \\ H_m &\triangleq \text{diag}[h_m(0) : h_m(N-1)] \end{aligned}$$

and let $C = [c_{n,k}]_{N \times N}$ is the N -point DCT-IV transform matrix with $c_{n,k}$ given by

$$c_{n,k} = \cos \frac{\pi(n+\frac{1}{2})(k+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \quad n, k = 0 : N-1$$

and $S = [s_{n,k}]_{N \times N}$ is the N -point DST-IV transform matrix with $s_{n,k}$ given by

$$s_{n,k} = \sin \frac{\pi(n+\frac{1}{2})(k+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \quad n, k = 0 : N-1$$

Note that, $C = C^T = \frac{N}{2}C^{-1}$ and $S = S^T = \frac{N}{2}S^{-1}$.

Equation (2) can be written, for $k = 0 : N-1$, as

$$\mathbf{x}_0 = \sum_{\substack{m=0 \\ m=\text{even}}}^{M-1} H_m C \mathbf{a}_m + \sum_{\substack{m=0 \\ m=\text{odd}}}^{M-1} H_m S \mathbf{a}_m \quad (3)$$

For $k = N : 2N-1$, (2) can be written as

$$x(\kappa + N) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} a_{m,n} h_{m-1}(\kappa) \text{csin} \frac{\pi(\kappa+N+\frac{1}{2})(n+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \quad (4)$$

where $\kappa = 0 : N-1$. From trigonometry,

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \frac{\pi(\kappa+N+\frac{1}{2})(n+\frac{1}{2})}{N} &= -\cos \frac{\pi(N-1-\kappa+\frac{1}{2})(n+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \\ \sin \frac{\pi(\kappa+N+\frac{1}{2})(n+\frac{1}{2})}{N} &= +\sin \frac{\pi(N-1-\kappa+\frac{1}{2})(n+\frac{1}{2})}{N} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, (4) can be put in matrix notation as

$$\mathbf{x}_1 = - \sum_{m=\text{even}} H_{m-1} J C \mathbf{a}_m + \sum_{m=\text{odd}} H_{m-1} J S \mathbf{a}_m \quad (5)$$

where J is the $N \times N$ row exchange matrix

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 1 & 0 \\ \vdots & \diagup & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Similarly, one can show that

$$\mathbf{x}_2 = - \sum_{m=\text{even}} H_{m-2} C \mathbf{a}_m - \sum_{m=\text{odd}} H_{m-2} S \mathbf{a}_m \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_3 = \sum_{m=\text{even}} H_{m-3} J C \mathbf{a}_m - \sum_{m=\text{odd}} H_{m-3} J S \mathbf{a}_m \quad (7)$$

Based on (3), (5), (6) and (7), rewriting (2) in matrix form, for $k = 0 : MN-1$, gives

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{a} \quad (\text{synthesis transform}) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{a} \triangleq [\mathbf{a}_0^T : \mathbf{a}_{M-1}^T]^T$ is a vectorized form of $a_{m,n}$ and $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_0^T : \mathbf{x}_{M-1}^T]^T$ is the discrete signal of length MN , $\mathbf{E}$ is an $MN \times MN$ orthogonal block-diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{E} = \text{diag}[C, S, -C, -S, \dots, C, S] \quad (9)$$

$\mathbf{E}$ represents the linear transformation. $\mathbf{H}$ is a $MN \times MN$ block matrix which provides the desired windowing effect and $\mathbf{H} = [\tilde{H}_{i,j}]_{M \times M}$ with $\tilde{H}_{i,j}$ given by

$$\tilde{H}_{i,j} = (-1)^{\lfloor \frac{i-j+1}{2} \rfloor} H_{i-j} J^{(i \bmod 2)} \quad (10)$$

where $\lfloor x/y \rfloor$ is the integer part of x/y and $x \bmod y$ is the remainder. The inverse of (8) is $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{E}^{-1} \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{x}$. Since $\mathbf{E}^{-1} = \frac{2}{N} \mathbf{E}$, thus

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{2}{N} \mathbf{E} \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{x} \quad (\text{analysis transform}) \quad (11)$$

$\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ is also $MN \times MN$ block matrix with diagonal or anti-diagonal blocks. The elements of $\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ comprise the resulting discrete biorthogonal functions $\gamma_m(k)$ [5], i.e.,

$$a_{m,n} = \frac{2}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{MN-1} \gamma_m(k) x(k) \text{csin} \frac{\pi(n+\frac{1}{2})(k+\frac{1}{2})}{N}$$

4 TRUNCATED-WINDOW TRANSFORM

In the following theorem, an interesting feature of the aperiodic SLTF transform (which does not hold for Gabor transform) will be proven. That is truncating the analysis window to be of length $2N$, the resulting biorthogonal function will be exactly of length $2N$. This means that using this $2N$ window and its $2N$ biorthogonal function, establishes a real-time SLTF transform without any approximation.

Theorem 1 For aperiodic SLTF transform, the biorthogonal function to any window of length $2N$ is of the same length.

Proof. Referring to the structure of $\mathbf{H}$ (10), if the window is of length $2N$ (i.e., $h(n)$ is zero outside the interval $[-\frac{N}{2} : \frac{3N}{2} - 1]$ and $H_{i,j} = 0$ except for $i - j = -1, 0, 1$), $\mathbf{H}$ will have the structure

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \diagup & & & & \\ & \diagup & & & \\ & & \diagup & & \\ & & & \diagup & \\ & & & & \diagup \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where the solid lines indicate the only non-zero elements in $\mathbf{H}$. The matrix $\mathbf{H}$ can be transformed to a block-diagonal matrix using the permutation matrices¹ $\mathbf{P}_1$ and $\mathbf{P}_2$ whose encoding vectors p_1 and p_1 are given by

$$\begin{aligned} p_1(k) &= \lfloor k/M \rfloor + N(k \bmod M) \\ p_2(k) &= l(N-1) + (-1)^l \lfloor k/M \rfloor + N(k \bmod M) \end{aligned}$$

for $k = 0 : MN - 1$ and $l = k \bmod 2$.

Since, permutation matrices are orthogonal,

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{P}_2^T (\mathbf{P}_2 \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_1) \mathbf{P}_1^T = \mathbf{P}_2^T \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_1^T \quad (13)$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}^{-1} = \mathbf{P}_1 \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{P}_2 = \left(\mathbf{P}_2^T \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{P}_1^T \right)^T \quad (14)$$

The matrix $\mathbf{H} \triangleq \mathbf{P}_2 \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_1$ is block-diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{H} = \text{diag} [\mathbf{D}_0 : \mathbf{D}_{N-1}] \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{D}_n$, for $n=0 : N-1$, are $M \times M$ block-diagonal matrices given by

$$\mathbf{D}_n = \begin{cases} \text{diag} [p_n, \mathbf{d}_n, \mathbf{d}_n, \dots, \mathbf{d}_n, q_n] & \text{for } n = 0 : \frac{N}{2} - 1 \\ \text{diag} [\mathbf{d}_{N-1-n}, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{N-1-n}] & \text{for } n = \frac{N}{2} : N-1 \end{cases}$$

where $p_n = h(n)$, $q_n = h(N-1-n)$, and $\mathbf{d}_n$ are a 2×2 matrices given by

$$\mathbf{d}_n \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} +h(N-n-1) & +h(-n-1) \\ -h(N+n) & +h(n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Since

$$\mathbf{D}_n^{-1} = \begin{cases} \text{diag} [p_n^{-1}, \mathbf{d}_n^{-1}, \dots, \mathbf{d}_n^{-1}, q_n^{-1}] & \text{for } n = 0 : \frac{N}{2} - 1 \\ \text{diag} [\mathbf{d}_{N-1-n}^{-1}, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{N-1-n}^{-1}] & \text{for } n = \frac{N}{2} : N-1 \end{cases}$$

and

$$\mathbf{H}^{-1} = \text{diag} [\mathbf{D}_0^{-1} : \mathbf{D}_{N-1}^{-1}] \quad (17)$$

¹The permutation matrix $\mathbf{P}$ is the identity matrix with rows re-ordered. $\mathbf{P}$ is represented by the encoding vector p whose element $p(k)$ is the column index of the sole "1" in k^{th} row of $\mathbf{P}$.

Therefore, $\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ is, like $\mathbf{H}$, a block-diagonal matrix with 1×1 and 2×2 blocks. As a consequence, from (13) and (14), $\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ has the transpose structure of $\mathbf{H}$ in (12), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{H}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \diagdown & & & & \\ & \diagdown & & & \\ & & \diagdown & & \\ & & & \diagdown & \\ & & & & \diagdown \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

From (11), the diagonal or anti-diagonal elements from each block in the m^{th} block row of $\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ constitute the biorthogonal function $\gamma_m(k)$ [5], which has only $2N$ non-zero elements. This illustrates why the truncation of the window to a length of $2N$ gives a biorthogonal function which has also a length of exactly $2N$ ■

The biorthogonal functions $\gamma_m(k)$ are the same except for $m = 0, M-1$. The truncated Gaussian window $h_m(k)$ and its biorthogonal function $\gamma_m(k)$ are plotted in Fig. 1 in both time and frequency domains for $m = 5$ and $\sigma = 1$. As shown from Fig. 1, both $h(k)$ and $\gamma(k)$ have good localization in both time and in frequency domains.

Figure 1: Truncated Gaussian window $h(t)$ and its biorthogonal function $\gamma(t)$ for $\sigma = 1$.

5 COMPUTATION SAVINGS

Transform computations consist of two parts as follows:

5.1 Computation of The Biorthogonal Function

Corollary 1 For any window of length $2N$, calculation of the biorthogonal functions $\gamma_m(k)$ requires $3.5N$ operations irrespective of the signal length.

Proof. The elements of $\mathbf{H}^{-1}$ comprise the resulting discrete biorthogonal function $\gamma_m(k)$. From (17), inversion of $\mathbf{H}$ requires inversion of the 2×2 matrices $\mathbf{d}_n$ and inversion of the elements p_n and q_n for $n = 0 : \frac{N}{2} - 1$. Assuming that the inversion of a 2×2 matrix takes 5 operations, calculating $\gamma_m(k)$ take $3.5N$ operations irrespective of the value of M . ■

According to the above corollary, calculation of $\gamma_m(k)$ requires $3.5N$ operations which is a drastic reduction compared with $\mathcal{O}(NM \log_2 M)$ for SLTF and Gabor transforms [2]. Moreover, $\gamma_m(k)$ are independent of the signal length. This means that one need not to recalculate $\gamma_m(k)$ for different signals with different lengths.

5.2 Computation of The Transform Coefficients

Referring to (11), (18), and (9), one can proceed to compute the m^{th} N transform coefficients as follows: Multiply the signal $x(k)$ by $\gamma_m(k)$. Let the product be denoted by y which is of length $2N$. Divide y into 4 sections $\{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4\}$ each is of length $\frac{N}{2}$. Let $z = (-1)^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} (y_2 + \overleftarrow{y_1}; y_3 - \overleftarrow{y_4})$, where $(x_1; x_2)$ denotes the concatenation of x_1 and x_2 and $\overleftarrow{y}$ denotes a reversed copy of y . Then if m is even, take the N -point DCT-IV transform of z and if m is odd, take the N -point DST-IV transform.

Assuming that the N -point DCT or DST takes $(\frac{N}{2} \log_2 N)$ multiplications, a total of $(2N + \frac{N}{2} \log_2 N)$ multiplications are required for each m . Thus, all $a_{m,n}$ require $(MN(2 + \frac{1}{2} \log_2 N))$ multiplications. Both SLTF transform [2] and the Zak transform-based algorithm for the Gabor transform [6] require $MN(\frac{1}{2} \log_2 N + \log_2 M + 1)$ multiplications. Thus, there is a saving of $\frac{2 + \frac{1}{2} \log_2 N}{\log_2 M + 1 + \frac{1}{2} \log_2 N}$.

6 CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROPOSED TRANSFORM

In this section, the proposed truncation is tested to assess whether it would adversely affect the good properties of the SLTF transform: mainly, stability and localization of the biorthogonal function.

6.1 Stability

Stability is an inherent characteristic of any transform which describes how perturbations in the signal in one domain affect the signal in the transformed domain. A precise measure of the sensitivity of any discrete linear transform $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{x}$ to perturbations of the signal $\mathbf{x}$ is defined by the condition number $\kappa(\mathbf{T}) = \|\mathbf{T}\| \|\mathbf{T}^{-1}\|$.

Referring to (8), to compare the stability of the proposed transform with the SLTF, the condition number $\kappa(\mathbf{HE})$ for Gaussian window ($\sigma = 1$) and typical values of M and N for both transforms (excluding the 2 edges $m = 0, M - 1$) are listed in Table 1. From Table 1, the proposed transform is even more stable than SLTF.

(N, M)	Proposed	SLTF [1]
(16, 16)	1.0718	1.1872
(32, 32)	1.0732	1.1887
(64, 64)	1.0735	1.1891
(256, 128)	1.0736	1.1892

Table 1: Condition number of the proposed transform compared to SLTF

6.2 Localization of $h(t)$ and $\gamma(t)$

The only price to be paid for this window truncation is the ripples appearing in the Gaussian window $h(t)$ and its biorthogonal function $\gamma(t)$ in the frequency domain due to truncation. The amplitudes of these ripples, however, are far less than the amplitude of the main lobe for practical values of σ . In Fig. 2, $h(t)$ and $\gamma(t)$ are plotted in the frequency domain for full-length Gaussian window and truncated Gaussian window for $\sigma = 1$. For $h(t)$, Fig. 2-(a), the ratio of the

Figure 2: Effect of truncating the Gaussian window in the frequency domain.

main lobe to the highest ripple is 26 for any M and N . For $\gamma(t)$, Fig. 2-(b), the ratio is 13.3 versus 23.5 for the SLTF transform. Therefore, these ripples have a negligible effect for all practical purposes.

7 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a real-time SLTF transform is proposed. The resulting transform has comparable properties with the SLTF. Specifically, the biorthogonal function, as in the SLTF transform, is well localized in both time and frequency. In addition, this transform is more stable and computationally more efficient than SLTF. The proposed transform requires $MN(2 + \frac{1}{2} \log_2 N)$ operations for computing transform coefficients and $3.5N$ operations for computing the biorthogonal function. It is worthy noting that, this truncated window transform leads to an exact reconstruction of the signal, and not just an approximation as the case in [3].

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